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D.8.5 Completed example of prototype designs for integration of various types of documentation and analytical data generated for a single object

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Abstract

This deliverable is an update of the initial closed, IPERION-CH deliverable D8.1. All the original figures, illustrating the semantic modelling of the people, objects and events involved in the documentation of heritage science have been extended to include full references to the core CIDOC CRMⁱ, and where appropriate directly related to real pieces of data, rather than just a theoretical outline.

Conservation and Heritage Science documentation are overarching terms used to cover the description and record of any relevant materials, activities, processes, people, places, and events involved in the history of a cultural heritage object. Cataloguing an object's composition, condition and how it has degraded or been damaged overtime, along with all the work that has been done to retard, treat and study this degradation process. So, this work can cover the full range of historic activities right up to the ever-increasing detail and complexity of modern scientific analytical techniques. The amount of time and expertise needed to record everything in a meaningful and re-usable fashion can rapidly progress past the level that is realistic for the many different specialists working in this field. A balance must be established between the effort and time required and the future benefit of the recorded information; key to this process is making use of appropriate tools to maximise the efficiency of the documentation process.

Over the last decade large amounts of time and money have been invested in the development of conservation-related documentation systemsⁱⁱ and digital toolsⁱⁱⁱ, to help with this documentation process. Some of this work has taken place within specific institutions while other larger projects, most notably the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation funded ConservationSpace^{iv} and ResearchSpace^v projects, have been developed through multi-institutional collaborations. However, these new tools and systems are often developed for specific purposes and can still require a fair amount of technical know-how or support to implement, populate and access. Also, even with all this work, many specialists in the field are still using simple digital file folders or are stuck with older institution-specific databases that struggle to meet their current requirements. In many cases people are also still working with analogue filing systems.

Additional research is required to provide a bridge between current working practice and any future complete integrated digital solution. This work-package has been developed to carry out some of this bridging work, examining and developing the new approaches to digital documentation being developed by the project partners. The work-package will also provide accessible, re-usable, practical worked examples of tools that can be used to document conservation work. Examining how they can be used to link together the important work that is already done, to make the captured information more accessible to others.

In order to connect existing work together and to identify where practical worked examples would be most informative, the relationships between the various types of documentary and analytical data generated for generic situations need to be described. This deliverable provides a series of more fully described, graphical examples demonstrating how the general semantic description of a specific painting and some generic concepts can be linked to the images and the results of their analytical examination. The descriptions and links defined within this deliverable have been developed from previous research work^{vi}, along with detailed discussions between the various participating partners.

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Abstract (for dissemination)	A series of described graphical representations of how the details of a specific object, documentation and analytical examination procedures can be semantically linked together in relation to the CIDOC CRM and several web-based thesauri.
Keywords	Conservation Documentation, Analytical Examination, Heritage Science, Semantic Relationships, Semantic Web, CIDOC-CRM, Linked Data

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Table 1: General abbreviations related to this document.

PID	Persistent identifier - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persistent_identifier
CIDOC-CRM	Centro Intercultural de Documentación Conceptual Reference Model - http://www.cidoc-crm.org/
LOD	Linked Open Data - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Linked_data
AAT	Art & Architecture Thesaurus - http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/index.html
ULAN	Union List of Artist Names - http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/ulan/index.html
TGN	Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names® Online - http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/index.html
IPERION-CH	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage - http://www.iperionch.eu/
DAM	Digital Asset Management (system)
WD	Wikidata - https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page
NG	The National Gallery – https://www.nationalgallery.org.uk/ and https://data.ng-london.org.uk

Table 2: Namespace abbreviations used in the diagrams

aat	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/
tgn	http://vocab.getty.edu/tgn/
ulan	http://vocab.getty.edu/ulan/
ng	https://data.ng-london.org.uk/
ngo	https://data.ng-london.org.uk/resource/
ngi	Internal NG namespace, these identifiers will not currently resolve outside of the NG.
crm	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/
wd	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/
rdfs	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
owl	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#

Introduction

Conservation and Heritage Science documentation are overarching terms used to cover the description and record of any relevant materials, activities, processes, people, places, and events involved in the history of a cultural heritage object. Cataloguing an object's composition, condition and how it has degraded or been damaged overtime, along with all the work that has been done to retard, treat and study this degradation process. So, this work can cover the full range of historic activities right up to the ever-increasing detail and complexity of modern scientific analytical techniques. The amount of time and expertise needed to record everything in a meaningful and re-usable fashion can rapidly progress past the level that is realistic for the many different specialists working in this field. A balance must be established between the effort and time required and the future benefit of the recorded information; key to this process is making use of appropriate tools to maximise the efficiency of the documentation process.

Over the last decade large amounts of time and money have been invested in the development of conservation-related documentation systems^{vii} and digital tools^{viii}, to help with this documentation process. Some of this work has taken place within specific institutions while other larger projects, most notably the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation funded ConservationSpace^{ix} and ResearchSpace^x projects, have been developed through multi-institutional collaborations. However, these new tools and systems are often developed for specific purposes and can still require a fair amount of technical know-how or support to implement, populate and access. Also, even with all this work, many specialists in the field are still using simple digital file folders or are stuck with older institution-specific databases that struggle to meet their current requirements. In many cases people are also still working with analogue filing systems.

Additional research is required to provide a bridge between current working practice and any future complete integrated digital solution. This work-package has been developed to carry out some of this bridging work, examining and developing the new approaches to digital documentation being developed by the project partners. The work-package will also provide accessible, re-usable, practical worked examples of tools that can be used to document conservation work. Examining how they can be used to link together the important work that is already done, to make the captured information more accessible to others.

The CIDOC CRM has continued to undergo development during this project, the references included in this document have been updated to try to reflect the latest draft version, which was version 6.2.7^{xi} as of the submission of this document. In addition to the development of the core CRM and number of additional compatible models^{xii} have been developed to provide additional ontological models for specific areas of research. The work presented in this deliverable could overlap with several of these extensions, particularly the CRMsci^{xiii}, which is being developed to help model scientific observations. However, as this CRMsci extension is still under active development it was decided that the work included in this deliverable would be limited to the core CRM ontology. This was done to examine how flexible the main standard could be and to help highlight where new simplifications or clarifications could enhance the included models.

Integration of documentary and analytical data generated for an object

In order to connect existing work together and to identify where the development of practical worked examples of documentation software would be most informative, the relationships between the various types of documentary and analytical data generated for generic and specific situations need to be described. This deliverable provides initial examples of how real objects can

be semantically described and linked to the images and the results of their analytical examination. All the linking properties and classes presented in the following sections are taken from the current release and development version of the CIDOC-CRM^{xiv} ontology. References to external control vocabularies or thesauri^{xv} have also been included to demonstrate how internal documentation systems can be linked to external resources.

This document does not cover all the possible relationships relating to conservation documentation but concentrates on examples of the main properties and values required to document and organise technical and analytical examinations of cultural heritage objects. Therefore, the semantic description of objects, their creators and common events will be minimal and will not explore the additional concepts more specifically related to detailed conservation treatments, art history, provenance or exhibitions. However, in addition to the demonstrating the semantic relationships between data types the examples included in this document have been extended to demonstrate how real literal values, numbers, dates, names and text can be connected to the semantic model. The data included in this deliverable has been taken from the online Raphael Research Resource^{xvi}.

In the following sections of this deliverable each of the sets of relationships are presented in the form of a flow diagram, which indicates and explains the entities being linked together and the properties connecting them. A key explaining the shapes and colours used within each of the flow diagrams can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Key for the flow diagrams included in this document. Most of the terms and phrases used are based on the terms used within the CIDOC-CRM^{xvii}, however the source of each, non-free text term, has been indicated with abbreviated namespace, such as “crm:E1...”, see **Table 2** for all of the abbreviated namespaces used in the diagrams.

Defined Semantic Relationships

Objects, Production Events, Creators and Further Events

Within this document, in the most generic sense an **object** is any physical or conceptual thing that needs to be discussed, examined or described. This can include complete cultural heritage objects such as paintings, sculptures, books & manuscripts, shards of pot, or even whole buildings. A specific **object** can also be a fragment, section or part of a complete cultural heritage object, such as a painting stretcher, scraps of paper, pieces of broken sculpture, and flakes of glaze/paint, or even analytical samples that have been deliberately removed. Actual museum objects, like paintings, are composed of several different sub-objects, such as paint layers, canvas, nail, etc. All of these different sub-objects can be described individually, if required.

Within this document, in the most generic sense a **creator/actor** is any person, groups or organisation responsible for the creation of a specific object in a **production event**. This can include artists, authors and even conservation scientists who might take a sample from an object or carry out analytical work.

Further events in an object's life can cover a wide range of activities, including the commissioning of the work, its movement, any alterations or conservation treatments, additional changes of ownership, etc. Describing, in detail, the full range of these **further events** goes beyond the scope of this deliverable, but the generic relationships common to most of them have been described.

Providing a full list of all the possible types of objects and creators that may be considered within conservation documentation goes well beyond the scope of this document. Where appropriate reference to and use of existing vocabularies^{xviii} will be used within this work-package to define or identify these types.

The schematic representations included in this document are intended to provide additional examples of how the CIDOC-CRM can be used to organise the documentation of conservation/heritage science. However, in addition to providing a theoretical model the diagrams have been extended to suggest how real pieces of data; the names, dates, numbers, texts, etc. can be directly linked to the models.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of some of the common semantic relationships that are documented between a specific object and the information recorded about it. In this case the “Further Events” could encompass all sorts of conservation treatments and interventions, though these are not examined specifically in this document.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of some of the common semantic relationships that are documented between the production event of a specific painting and the information recorded about it.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of some of the common semantic relationships that are documented between a specific creator or artist, the information recorded about them and how they can be connected to specific production events.

Figure 5: A range of further events and activities are captured as part of conservation and heritage science documentation from object movements to analytical examinations or simple condition checking. This schematic representation displays some of the more common relationships shared by these events.

Taking Samples

In the process of taking a sample from a heritage object a new object, the sample, is created. The main documentation issues to consider during a sampling procedure are to capture details and the location of the sample site and to record the reason and description of the actual part removal event, see Figure 6, additional textual statements may also be needed and can be added as required.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of some of the more common semantic relationships that can be documented during the process of taking and describing a sample from a given painting.

Figure 8: Extension of **Figure 7**, providing some additional data directly related to the actual visual item or digital image version of the image created in the simple image based examination. This schematic does not cover additional information in relation to any digitisation or scanning events.

Defining Areas of Interest and Image Annotation

A large part of conservation documentation is related to describing or examining specific parts of an object, “Areas of Interest”. These “Areas” are commonly described as free text but is often helpful to mark them down by directly annotating appropriate images. Image annotation involves the identification of each specific “area of interest” on an image and capturing its specific location, size, and shape. The annotation can then be linked to a simple description or more complex further documentation, as required, in some form of presentation. Figure 9 shows the common relationships shared between defining “Areas of Interest” and annotating images.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of some of the more common semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the process of identifying an “area of interest” and recording it as an annotation relative to a specific image.

Describing Measurements and Analytical Examinations

Conservation or Heritage science makes use of a wide range of analytical processes to examine, measure, and identify objects and the materials that they are composed of. The data gathered can range from a simple number to a complex multi-dimensional data array or images and spectra. In this section the generic relationships and events involved in all these processes have been broken down into stages, represented by a few specific examples. For more complex forms of analysis several of these stages would need to be joined together and, in some cases, this would need to be done several times. In the schematic diagrams shown in this section the term “Dimension” has been used to cover all types of single or groups of measured values, from simple widths and heights to more complex spectra and 3D data cubes. In addition, to allow the definition of further relationships the CIDOC CRM term “Information Object” has also been used to represent “data sets” as a whole.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of some of the more common semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the examination of a sample using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy^{xix}.

Capturing and Describing Simple Numerical Values

Following a measurement process, similar to the one shown in Figure 10, simple numerical values can be documented as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Schematic representation of the semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the capture of a simple numerical.

Capturing and Describing Analytical Data

This schematic also covers the notion of exploring nested multi-dimensional analytical data which was covered in D8.1, as shown in **Figure 26**.

Figure 12: Schematic representation of the semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the documentation of more complex analytical data sets. The optional transformations of dimensions or data sets would produce new resources that would need to be documented in the same way, see **Figure 13**.

Processing or transforming data sets

Figure 13 Extension of **Figure 12**, providing details of how one would model working with processed or normalised data sets and versioning.

Areas of future work and exploitation.

The models included in this deliverable are intended as the foundation of future work, contributing to the process of building a consensus relating to how the CIDOC CRM can be practically used to model actual conservation/heritage science data and to highlight what might be required from software systems used to capture and store this data.

Collaboration, dissemination and further development

The models included in this deliverable only use the core CIDOC CRM ontology and have not required the use of any of the current CRM extensions. However, as these extensions are further developed it is recommended that they are considered as part of any future development of the work presented within this deliverable, in order to potentially improve or simplify the relationships needed to model and the document conservation/heritage science research. In addition to this, consideration of other additional related research projects, such as <https://linked.art> and <https://www.ligatus.org.uk/lcd> , will also contribute to the production of accessible, practical examples of how complex semantics can be really used.

Also, in order to make it easier for the work included within this deliverable to be updated, corrected, improved, re-used, developed and expanded, each of the individual models are going to be uploaded to an open software repository on Github^{xx}. Here the models, and any related software used to create them, can be discussed and edited, complete with a robust versioning system to allow people to reference, cite and keep track of dated versions of the models.

Exploring new ways to present semantic graphical model

The diagram included in this deliverable where created directly within Microsoft Word 365, following on from the initial diagrams created within D8.1. However, it has become clear that including and working with more complex diagrams, in this way, can be a slow inefficient process

and the models can be cumbersome and time consuming to edit to accommodate further relationships. Some initial experiments have been carried out with alternative methods of automatically creating this type of schematic model directly from simple lists of text based semantic relationships, using a piece of software called Mermaid^{xxi}, see Figure 14. It is recommended that further work in this area makes use of this type of automated process, to make it easier to develop existing models and to aid the collaborative development of new ones.

Figure 14: An example of an automatically generated schematic diagram, based on the data included in Figure 2, generated using a software package called Mermaid^{xxii}.

Direct re-use within future projects

Further re-use and development of the semantic models included in this deliverable are already planned within two additional EU H2020 projects SSHOC and IPERION-HS.

Within SSHOC^{xxiii} this work will be specifically used within a task looking to create example FAIR^{xxiv} datasets based on existing cultural heritage datasets, also including the work reported in the IPERION-CH deliverable D8.6.

Within IPERION-HS^{xxv} this work will be used to help define the semantic models needed to create/select interoperable file formats, procedure and method statements that will be used to document collaborative Heritage Science research activities.

Appendix A – D8.1 Diagrams

The following figures are included from the initial deliverable, D8.1, for reference.

Figure 15: Key for the flow diagrams included in this appendix. Most of the terms and phrases used are based on the terms used within the CIDOC-CRM^{xxvi}.

Figure 16: Initial schematic representation of some of the common semantic relationships that are documented between a generic object and the information recorded about it. In this case the “Further Events” could encompass all sorts of conservation treatments and interventions, though these are not examined specifically in this document. Original version of **Figure 2**.

Figure 17: Initial schematic representation of some of the common semantic relationships that are documented between a generic production event and the information recorded about it. Original version of **Figure 3**.

Figure 18: Initial schematic representation of some of the common semantic relationships that are documented between a generic creator or artist and the information recorded about them. Original version of **Figure 4**.

Figure 19: Initial schematic representation of the range of further events and activities are captured as part of conservation documentation from object movements to condition checking. This schematic representation displays some of the more common relationships shared by these events. Original version of **Figure 5**.

Figure 20: Initial schematic representation of some of the more common semantic relationships that can be documented during the process of taking samples. Original version of **Figure 6**.

Figure 21: Initial schematic representation of some of the more common semantic relationships that can be documented during the process of capturing images of cultural heritage objects or samples. Original version of **Figure 7**.

Figure 24: Initial schematic representation of the semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the capture of a simple numerical. Original version of **Figure 11**.

Figure 25: Initial schematic representation of the semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the capture of more complex analytical data sets. The optional transformations of Dimensions or Data Points would produce new Dimensions and Data points that would need to be documented in the same way, as indicated with double headed arrows. Original version of **Figure 12**.

Figure 26: Initial schematic representation of; **A:** the semantic relationships that can be recorded in relation to the capture of very complex nested analytical data sets, such as 3D numerical data sets like Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectroscopy, or spectroscopic mapping techniques like X-ray Fluorescence -Mapping and HyperSpectral Imaging. **B:** Specific example based on Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectroscopy analysis. This particular figure has not been extended in this deliverable as the relevant relationships have been added to **Figure 12**.

References

- ⁱ “The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage.” - <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>
- ⁱⁱ <http://www.rembrandtdatabase.org/>, <http://www.lucascranach.org/>, <http://boschproject.org/>, <http://cima.ng-london.org.uk/documentation> (Raphael Research Resource).
- ⁱⁱⁱ Such as Image viewers (e.g. <http://iiif.io/>), ontologies (e.g. <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>) and open linked vocabularies (e.g. <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/lod/>).
- ^{iv} <http://www.conservationspace.org/>, <https://sites.google.com/site/conservationspace/>
- ^v <http://www.researchspace.org/>
- ^{vi} Padfield, J. and A. Gent. 2014. Making complex documentation simpler: Combining existing resources with MediaWiki to provide a flexible documentation platform. In ICOM-CC 17th Triennial Conference Preprints, Melbourne, 15–19 September 2014, ed. J. Bridgland, art. 0202, 7 pp. Paris: International Council of Museums.(ISBN 978-92-9012-410-8)
- ^{vii} <http://www.rembrandtdatabase.org/>, <http://www.lucascranach.org/>, <http://boschproject.org/>, <http://cima.ng-london.org.uk/documentation> (Raphael Research Resource).
- ^{viii} Such as Image viewers (e.g. <http://iiif.io/>), ontologies (e.g. <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>) and open linked vocabularies (e.g. <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/lod/>).
- ^{ix} <http://www.conservationspace.org/>, <https://sites.google.com/site/conservationspace/>
- ^x <http://www.researchspace.org/>
- ^{xi} <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/Version/version-6.2.7>
- ^{xii} <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/collaborations>
- ^{xiii} <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmsci/>
- ^{xiv} “New draft version of the CIDOC CRM, version 6.2.1, encoded in RDFS” can be found at <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/versions-of-the-cidoc-crm> along with newer draft versions.
- ^{xv} The two main external LOD vocabularies/thesauri referenced in this document are the Getty’s AAT (<http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>) and Wikidata (<https://www.wikidata.org>).
- ^{xvi} The many website for the Raphael Research Resource can be found at: <https://cima.ng-london.org.uk>. An additional linked data version of all the data stored in the resource, along with a SPARQL end-point, can be accessed at <https://rdf.ng-london.org.uk/workshops/lcd> .
- ^{xvii} <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>
- ^{xviii} The descriptions and sub classification of a cultural heritage object and artists can be explored at: <http://www.getty.edu/vow/AATFullDisplay?find=&logic=AND¬e=&subjectid=300311889> and <http://www.getty.edu/vow/AATFullDisplay?find=&logic=AND¬e=&page=1&subjectid=300025103>, also reference to common historic artists can also be made via <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/ulan/index.html>.
- ^{xix} https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gas_chromatography%E2%80%93mass_spectrometry
- ^{xx} <https://github.com/jpadfield/cidoc-crm.examples>
- ^{xxi} <https://mermaidjs.github.io>
- ^{xxii} <https://mermaidjs.github.io>
- ^{xxiii} <https://sshopencloud.eu/> - "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782
- ^{xxiv} Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable: <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>
- ^{xxv} Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science – this is an new H2020 project which has just been accepted, but will not begin until early 2020.
- ^{xxvi} <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>